

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cadmium with some Amino Acids and Formic Acid. A Polarographic Study

FARID KHAN* and KRISHNA NEMA

Department of Chemistry, Doctor Hari Singh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 003

Manuscript received 10 September 1987, revised 20 June 1988, accepted 23 August 1988

An appreciable change due to side-chain and basicity of ligand on stability constants ($\log \beta$) of Cd^{II} complexes with glycine, α -alanine, L-valine, L-leucine, L-asparagine and L-glutamine as primary ligands and formic acid as the secondary ligand has been observed at pH 8.50 and at an ionic strength $\mu=1.0 M$ (potassium nitrate). Cd^{II} forms 1:1:1, 1:1:2, and 1:2:1 complexes at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The trend of stability constants of Cd^{II} with respect to amino acids and formic acid is L-glutamine < L-asparagine < L-valine < L-leucine < α -alanine < glycine which is explained on the basis of sizes and basicities of these ligands.

THE uses of amino acid derivatives in biology, medicine and as reagents have been known¹. Various compounds of Cd^{II} with amino acids and different other acids have also been reported from this laboratory². A survey of literature reveals that no ternary complexes of Cd^{II} with glycine, α -alanine, L-valine, L-leucine, L-asparagine and L-glutamine and formic acid have been reported so far. Hence the authors report the studies on ternary complexes of Cd^{II} with these acids with the view to determine the effect of side-chain and basicities of ligands on the stabilities of the complexes.

Experimental

All the reagents were of A.R. grade. The purities of amino acids were checked by chromatography³ and the solutions prepared in conductivity water. The concentrations of the metal ion, potassium nitrate and gelatin in the test solution were 1.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.001%, respectively.

All the complexes exhibited maximum shifts of $E_{1/2}$ at pH range 8.50 selected for the present study.

Current-voltage measurements were made on a manual polarograph using a Toshniwal PL-50 Polyflex galvanometer. The capillary characteristics were $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$ at 60.0 cm effective height of mercury. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the test solution before recording the current-voltage data. A Elico LI-10 pH-meter was used to measure pH values of the solutions which were adjusted at 8.50 with dilute solutions of NaOH and HNO_3 as required. The entire study was carried out at $25 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

A well-defined two-electron reversible reduction wave of Cd^{II} was observed in KNO_3 . The plots of

$\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ gave straight lines with slopes $30 \pm 1 \text{ mV}$ (mean value) showing two-electron reversible reduction of Cd^{II} and of all its complexes. A number of current-voltage curves were obtained for the binary complexes prior to the study of the ternary complexes.

Cd-amino acids system: The pK_a values of amino acids were determined by titration method⁴ (Table 1). These values are in good agreement

TABLE 1— pK VALUES OF AMINO ACIDS

Amino acids	pK_1	pK_2
Glycine	2.40	9.80
α -Alanine	2.50	9.40
L-Valine	2.28	9.71
L-Leucine	2.92	9.74
L-Glutamine	2.17	9.18
L-Asparagine	2.02	8.80

with the reported values⁵. The concentration of the free ligand was calculated from the pK_a value and pH of the test solution. Deford and Hume's method⁶ was used to determine the composition and stability constants of binary complexes. The data and plots of $F_1[X]$ vs $[\text{gly}]$ are given in Tables 2 and 3 and Fig. 1, respectively.

Cd-formate system: The reversible diffusion-controlled wave had $E_{1/2}$'s whose plot had straight line portions showing the formation of successive complexes. Lingane's method⁷ revealed the formation of $[\text{Cd}(\text{for})]^{+1}$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{for})_2]$ complexes with stability constants, $\log \beta_{01} = 2.26$ and $\log \beta_{02} = 3.80$, respectively.

Cd-amino acids formate system: The system was studied at pH 8.5 by keeping the concentration of formic acid constant at 0.005 and 0.01 M, while varying the concentration of each amino acid from 1.0 to 10.0 mM. The single waves obtained were

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC AND DERIVED DATA FOR Cd-GLYCINATE SYSTEM

[CdII]=1.0 mM, $\mu=1.0$ M (KNO₃), pH=8.5, $(E_{1/2})_M=0.586$ V (vs SOE)

[gly] M	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ V	$\log I_m/I_0$	$F_0[X]$	$F_1[X]$ $\times 10^{-4}$	$F_2[X]$ $\times 10^{-7}$	$F_3[X]$ $\times 10^{-9}$
0.00	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.000 5	0.040	0.007 17	22 94	4.98	—	—
0.001	0.053	0.014 4	64.25	6.92	4.82	8.25
0.002	0.070	0.014 4	241.65	12.03	5.01	5.08
0.003	0.080	0.021 9	585.92	17.88	5.27	4.25
0.004	0.088	0.021 9	999 58	24.96	5.74	4.85
0.005	0.094	0.029 4	1 623.15	32.44	6.08	4.17
0.006	0.100	0.037 1	2 636.93	43.93	6.98	4.93
0.007	0.104	0.037 1	3 601.30	51.43	7.06	4.87
0.008	0.108	0.044 9	5 007.48	62.58	7.57	4.46
0.010	0.115	0.044 9	8 639.72	86.38	8.43	4.43

$\log \beta_{10}=4.80$, $\log \beta_{20}=7.60$, $\log \beta_{30}=9.64$.

Fig. 1. Values of $F_1[X]$ for cadmium in glycinate medium: (○) $F_0[X] \times 10^{-1}$, (●) $F_1[X] \times 10^{-4}$, (△) $F_2[X] \times 10^{-7}$, and (□) $F_3[X] \times 10^{-9}$.

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY COMPLEXES OF CdII

Ligand	Stability constant*		
	$\log \beta_{10}$	$\log \beta_{20}$	$\log \beta_{30}$
Glycine	4.80	7.60	9.64
α -Alanine	4.23	7.46	9.43
L-Valine	4.11	7.21	9.16
L-Leucine	4.17	7.35	9.34
L-Glutamine	4.00	7.04	8.91
L-Asparagine	4.07	7.18	9.10

*Original values upto 4th decimal place.

reversible and diffusion-controlled. Schaap and McMasters method⁸ confirmed the formation of 1:1:1, 1:1:2 and 1:2:1 complexes of CdII with glycine, α -alanine, L-valine, L-leucine, L-glutamine and L-asparagine and formic acid. The results and the plots of $F_{ij}[X,Y]$ vs [gly] are given in Tables 4–6 and Figs. 2 and 3, respectively. The equilibria for [Cd-gly-for], [Cd- α -ala-for], [Cd-L-val-for], [Cd-L-leu-for], [Cd-L-asp-for] and [Cd-L-glut-for] systems are given in Schemes 1–6, respectively.

TABLE 4—POLAROGRAPHIC AND DERIVED DATA FOR Cd-GLYCINATE-FORMATE SYSTEM

[for]=0.005 M, $\mu=1.0$ M (KNO₃), pH=8.5, $(E_{1/2})_M=-0.586$ V (vs SOE)

[gly] M	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ V	$\log I_m/I_0$	$F_{00}[X,Y]$ $\times 10^{-1}$	$F_{10}[X,Y]$ $\times 10^{-4}$	$F_{20}[X,Y]$ $\times 10^{-7}$	$F_{30}[X,Y]$ $\times 10^{-9}$
0.00	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.000 5	0.041	0.007 17	2.48	4.56	—	—
0.001	0.055	0.014 4	6.94	4.94	—	—
0.002	0.073	0.021 9	31.06	14.58	5.26	—
0.003	0.082	0.021 9	67.70	21.90	5.96	—
0.004	0.092	0.021 9	136 51	33.62	7.40	7.25
0.005	0.100	0.029 4	259.05	51.41	9.48	9.96
0.006	0.106	0.029 4	413 46	68.57	10.76	10.43
0.007	0.111	0.037 1	621.35	88.47	12.06	10.81
0.008	0.115	0.037 1	849.59	105.82	12.72	10.27
0.010	0.123	0.037 1	1 582.77	158.07	15.40	10.90

$\log A=0.90$, $\log B=4.60$, $\log C=7.65$, $\log D=10.02$.

TABLE 5—POLAROGRAPHIC AND DERIVED DATA FOR Cd-GLYCINATE-FORMATE SYSTEM

[for]=0.01 M, $\mu=1.0$ M (KNO₃), pH=8.5, (E_{1/2})_M = -0.586 V (vs SOE)

[gly] M	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ V	log I _m /I ₀	F ₀₀ [X,Y] × 10 ⁻¹	F ₁₀ [X,Y] × 10 ⁻⁴	F ₃₀ [X,Y] × 10 ⁻⁷	F ₅₀ [X,Y] × 10 ⁻⁹
0.000	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.000 5	0.050	0.014 4	5.08	9.97	—	—
0.001	0.062	0.021 9	18.18	9.18	—	—
0.002	0.074	0.029 4	43.15	19.57	5.78	—
0.003	0.086	0.029 4	87.02	27.67	6.55	—
0.004	0.098	0.037 1	225.65	55.41	11.85	—
0.005	0.105	0.037 1	389.81	77.06	18.81	17.13
0.006	0.110	0.044 9	585.19	96.86	14.81	16.85
0.007	0.115	0.044 9	868.97	122.85	16.40	16.29
0.008	0.120	0.052 9	1 275.55	158.94	18.86	17.38
0.010	0.128	0.052 9	2 241.71	223.72	21.57	16.57

log A=0.60, log B=4.90, log C=7.69, log D=10.23.

Fig. 2. Values of F_{ij} for cadmium-glycinate-formate system: (○) F₀₀[X,Y] × 10⁻¹, (●) F₁₀[X,Y] × 10⁻⁴, (Δ) F₃₀[X,Y] × 10⁻⁷ and (□) F₅₀[X,Y] × 10⁻⁹.

Fig. 3. Values of F_{ij}[X,Y] for cadmium-glycinate-formate system: (○) F₀₀[X,Y] × 10⁻¹, (●) F₁₀[X,Y] × 10⁻⁴, (Δ) F₃₀[X,Y] × 10⁻⁷ and (□) F₅₀[X,Y] × 10⁻⁹.

Diagram 1. [Cd-gly-for] system.

Diagram 2. [Cd-ala-for] system.

Diagram 3. [Cd-L-val-for] system.

Diagram 4. [Cd-L-leu-for] system.

Diagram 5. [Cd-L-asp-for] system.

